

The Linguistic Barrier and Social Critique from Multicultural Perspectives within the BRICS+ Salvador Summer School

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Abstract

This article examines linguistic barriers in international academic initiatives connected to the BRICS, focusing on the experience of the BRICS+ Salvador Summer School in Brazil. It analyzes how the adoption of English as the official language, although justified by its role as a global lingua franca, may reproduce historical inequalities linked to colonial linguistic hierarchies. Based on decolonial perspectives and brief testimonies from participants, the article highlights how limited access to English education can restrict participation, reduce knowledge assimilation, and create unequal opportunities among students from different socioeconomic and educational backgrounds. While English facilitates international communication and academic exchange, its exclusive use may also overshadow the linguistic and cultural identity of the host country and contradict the BRICS discourse that values plurality and Global South representation. The article therefore discusses possible alternatives to reduce linguistic barriers, such as the use of artificial intelligence for real-time translation, intercommunication practices with bilingual mediators, and investments in multilingual and decolonial language education. It concludes that addressing linguistic inequality is essential for aligning BRICS academic initiatives with the bloc's broader principles of diversity, inclusion, and cultural sovereignty.

Keywords: Linguistic Barriers; Plurilinguism; Decoloniality; BRICS

Introduction

Initially presented as an essential fundamental right, linguistic access often reveals itself more as a factor of social distancing than of social connection. Carrying several paradigms that prevent it from effectively becoming a guaranteed right that provides broad and clear communication to those who can understand it, access itself becomes difficult and selective. Languages, therefore, become a mechanism through which full understanding among their speakers can occur; thus, those who possess this knowledge are able to communicate and be understood.

Historically, language has been used as a tool to assume a dominant and powerful role. During the colonial period, imperial powers used their languages as a form of indoctrination over other peoples, completely erasing the cultures that existed there; it was the beginning of colonial monolingualism. As Antônio Bispo dos Santos (2023) states in *A terra dá, a terra quer*: “Colonialism did not dominate only territories; it also tried to dominate ways of thinking, speaking, and producing knowledge.” This process functioned as a form of ethnocide affecting entire civilizations, creating a linguistic dependency that continues to shape the world today. This dynamic was later described as **colonial glottopolitics**, reinforcing the condition of dominated peoples who remain linguistically dependent.

Within this framework, it is possible to analyze the context of the BRICS, where linguistic barriers become an extremely relevant issue in its debates. The cultural diversity present within the bloc can represent both an opportunity and a challenge, particularly when a consensus on communication must be established among countries that possess a wide range of possible languages that could be chosen as official ones. As an example, I present the course from which I draw this experience, the BRICS+ Salvador Summer School. This program was designed to bring together students from all countries participating in the economic bloc, and the chosen form of linguistic accessibility was the use of English as a lingua franca responsible for enabling communication between participants. This represents a clear case of exocommunication, in which two interlocutors use a third language to make communication possible between them. However, neither the international students nor the host country’s participants have English as their native language, removing everyone from their comfort zones in favor of a historically colonizing language.

Therefore, the problem established in this scenario describes a process of inequality forming within the bloc through the use of a language that does not correspond to any of the member countries. It is inevitable to address the difficulties created by this selectivity in enabling communication, where those who had better access to education during their formative years will consequently have greater access to opportunities that require this linguistic knowledge. As a result, social and educational inequalities are reproduced, privileging those with greater access while disadvantaging those with fewer opportunities, turning language into a mechanism of social selection.

As a form of reflection and resistance, I proposed to write about this topic and highlight its impact on the lives of students. For this text, I conducted a basic survey among both international and Brazilian participants in order to understand their perspectives and views on the topic. Using the question, “In your opinion, what are the positive and/or negative aspects of choosing English as the official language of the course?”, I interviewed my colleagues and was able to understand the issues that concerned them. From this, I present a brief analysis based on a multicultural perspective on how these linguistic barriers are perceived.

BRICS+ and Their Comiments

The BRICS, at the time of its creation, evoked the idea of a reformulation of the world order, emphasizing the independence that the Global South sought in relation to the Global North. Initially composed of Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa, the group aimed, through its union, to emerge on the global stage with an identity distinct from a Eurocentric and Americentric perspective. Although its initial impulses as a bloc were primarily economic, this alliance quickly evolved into the political and epistemological spheres, advocating for a more plural and counter-hegemonic world.

From the beginning, BRICS has adopted a strong position regarding external dependence, emphasizing the importance of state sovereignty among all countries while guaranteeing and valuing their diverse cultures. This stance reinforces its decolonial ideology as one of the guiding principles of the bloc. For this reason, it becomes problematic that the practices adopted within the bloc and in parallel discussions—such as the BRICS+ Salvador Summer School—raise questions that are both simple and complex at the same time.

In the realm of language, the debate over the use of English becomes fragile and reveals inequalities that historically helped shape the current global powers. In international relations, a common language of understanding is indeed necessary; however, it is equally important that multilingualism be preserved. In this sense, BRICS should actively address this issue within its committees and discussions, given its seriousness and its real implications for the bloc’s decolonial aspirations.

Positives Aspects of Using the English

To begin the discussion of what may or may not be considered a positive aspect of the use of English, it is necessary to turn our attention to decolonial literature. As discussed in the text *Línguas Como Recursos: Educação Linguística Intercultural e Inclusiva no Cenário dos BRICS*, Edleise Mendes (2020) presents the following perspective:

“Understanding languages as resources means giving language education a leading role, since it is one of the privileged strategies for the promotion of information, knowledge and social inclusion for all people, in an equitable and democratic way.”

In my research, I had the opportunity to interview Russians, a Mozambican, a South African, and a Brazilian. Unanimously, their responses regarding the positive aspects involved opportunities for study, exchange programs, employment, and communication with people from different countries. However, it is precisely at this point that it becomes necessary to observe a pattern. It is not simply the mastery of more than one language that grants individuals these opportunities; rather, it is the English language—the established *lingua franca*—that determines who will have access to spaces of privilege and prestige. In a broader sense, it is an exclusive language, as it does not necessarily allow for multilingualism or the full realization of the principles of linguistic access.

Personally, I am very grateful for the opportunity to understand what people from such different cultures and parts of the world had to say. This shared language enabled us to have that discussion. I firmly believe in the power of communication through foreign languages and I consistently advocate for learning new ways to communicate. However, I am fully aware that having this kind of access is a privilege—one that, for example, a Brazilian colleague in the course did not have. The simple lack of access to learning a foreign language becomes an exclusionary factor that could prevent someone from participating in an educational event of such significance, even when it is hosted in their own country.

It is also possible to observe many international cases in which a basic command of the English language can significantly impact the lives of immigrants. Amid bureaucratic processes, documentation requirements, and the search for employment, communication becomes essential. In this context, English often assumes this role in much of the world, functioning as a *lingua franca* and, in some ways, facilitating intercultural access and interaction.

Negatives Aspects Of Using The English

The trivialization of the use of English in international discussions may sometimes be justified by its role as a *lingua franca*. However, when we enter the context of BRICS+ and debates related to the Global South, it becomes necessary that, just as we advocate for economic independence, we also advocate for cultural independence and the state sovereignty that is highly valued within this geopolitical bloc. To declare oneself decolonial while still lacking concrete agendas regarding the disengagement from a colonizing language as the sole means of general communication represents a major contradiction and should be recognized as such.

One of the main problems related to the use of English as the official language of this course is the reproduction of social inequalities. A brief analysis of the Brazilian context reveals how precarious access to foreign language education can be, exposing a clear inequality that segregates knowledge. In public schools, language instruction does not reach the same level as that provided by prestigious bilingual institutions, which educate multilingual students from early childhood. Thus, what initially appears to be a method of inclusion ultimately

becomes exclusive, restricting full access to knowledge and academic participation.

Another important point to consider is the obstacle to the assimilation of knowledge. Using a second language to transmit and receive valuable information is not always fully effective. When individuals are removed from their linguistic comfort zones during moments of theoretical exchange, their level of mastery may partially decline, preventing full comprehension and often leading to more superficial learning. Alongside this issue is the inaccessibility of materials, a concern raised by several students who felt that a potential opportunity for greater inclusion was instead placed further out of reach.

Another relevant aspect is the fact that the exclusive use of English can overshadow the role of the host country, in this case, Brazil. The common expectation of an international course is that the culture of the host nation will be prominently present, allowing participants to truly immerse themselves in a new cultural environment. Instead, what emerges is a dependence on a language external even to the bloc being discussed. For example, a Mozambican student participating in the course arrived in Brazil only to discover that he would not be able to benefit from one of the few similarities between his home country and the host nation. Despite sharing the same language, Portuguese, he was required to speak a second language in order to communicate with people who could already understand him in his native tongue.

The predominance of English in academic environments can also contribute to the weakening or loss of linguistic and cultural identity. It is extremely important to understand the place in which we are being inserted, the beliefs, customs, and social practices that define it. Linguistic barriers often cause these elements to be lost along the way. Therefore, the choice of English is not merely a technical one; unfortunately, it is also political and social. Using it as the primary language in discussions about countries that are culturally rich and diverse ultimately represents a significant contradiction.

The Ways For the Future

In the face of the challenges caused by linguistic barriers in international academic contexts, it is essential to discuss strategies that can make these spaces more accessible while still respecting the linguistic plurality of states. Among these strategies, one of the most recent is the use of artificial intelligence for the simultaneous translation of debates and negotiations. This technology enables a more efficient and agile understanding of international communication. Although these tools still require improvements, they have already begun to make a significant difference in facilitating discourse across languages, making discussions more accessible even to those who do not have proficiency in English.

Another relevant communication strategy is intercommunication, in which interlocutors use their own languages with the mediation of a translator who has mastery of both languages involved. In this way, there is no need to rely on an external language to make communication

possible. This practice is used in various diplomatic and institutional contexts and contributes to the preservation of linguistic diversity.

Alongside technological solutions, it is also essential to recognize the need for investments in educational policies aimed at a decolonial approach to languages. In order to value cultural diversity, it is crucial to approach language education critically, acknowledging the historical power relations that have shaped the hierarchy among languages in the international system. Encouraging multilingualism is fundamental, as languages should be understood not only as tools of communication but also as expressions of identity and forms of knowledge.

An important example of the preservation of multilingualism can be observed in South Africa, which officially recognizes eleven languages within its territory. Through policies that encourage linguistic diversity, the country has managed to build a social organization in which different languages are present in educational, institutional, and cultural spheres. This model can serve as an important example within BRICS+, demonstrating that cultural diversity can be sustained through public policies and investments in the institutional structures necessary to support it.

Conclusions

Finally, in concluding the analysis presented in this article, I argue that the choice of English as the official language of the BRICS+ Salvador Summer School is not merely a technical or didactic decision. Rather, it reveals a series of historical and social processes that make this choice a problem worthy of critical examination. The inequalities and exclusions surrounding the dissemination of knowledge are evident, and they even appear in situations experienced during the course itself, such as when a student without proficiency in English was questioned by other classmates about her use of artificial intelligence to understand the proposed material.

Since its formation, the BRICS economic bloc has advocated distancing itself from colonial structures while valuing global plurality and representation. However, it is precisely at this point that this principle must be applied in all areas. It is essential to distance ourselves from historical imperialism in every aspect, especially in those that enable communication. A transformation in the system is necessary so that the group's practices remain consistent with its original discourse, allowing it to move away from all mechanisms of oppression and submission.

Although English indeed enables many experiences and exchanges, the future can be different. New possibilities may emerge, and perhaps there will eventually be a true sovereignty of multilingualism. It is necessary to promote the dissemination of knowledge in other languages and to ensure that, in an accessible way, diverse languages can occupy academic, social, and cultural spaces.

It therefore becomes clear that this topic must be debated urgently, carefully, and thoughtfully. Through already established methods and new approaches that may emerge, this discussion has the potential to expand significantly, encouraging deeper reflection on the role of language in academic programs connected to BRICS+ and beyond. It is understood, therefore, that it is up to BRICS+ and the younger generations that will follow it to recognize these debates and promote discussions that align institutional practices with the principles of the bloc itself.

I conclude this article by thanking my colleagues for their extremely valuable testimonies. I am also grateful to Professor Milan Puh for prioritizing the discussion of this topic, and to the student from the 2025 edition of the BRICS+ Salvador Summer School who described this process so insightfully. Finally, it was a pleasure to bring attention to a theme as important as the appreciation of our culture. I hope that we may always take pride in who we are and that we will never need to bow to colonial impositions.

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